

ACCST Research Journal

ISSN 0972-7779

Volume-XXIV, No. 1, January 2026

Journal website: <https://internationaljournalsiwan.com/research-journals.php>

ORCID Link: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6661-0289>

International Impact Factor: **8.625** <https://impactfactorservice.com/home/journal/2297>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=KJ4eXesAAAAJ&hl=en>

Refereed and Peer-Reviewed Quarterly Journal

Suitability of Skill Development & Vocational Courses in Motivating Students' Minds for Career Building

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(Received: November 24, 2025; Accepted: December 24, 2025; Published Online: January 31, 2026)

Abstract:

Through the National Education Policy 2020, steps and policies are being made in such a way that India can also contribute to providing inclusivity and equity in education under agenda 30. The most intriguing and sagacious decision that has been taken under this is to train the students for the future from their school and college life. Transforming them from apprentices to specialists who can use their skills and vocational training in earning their livelihood and contribute directly and indirectly towards adding income to the national economy. Several initiatives such as Skill India Digital Hub, Skill

[1]

India Programme, various skill-based courses at the institutional level, Bachelor of Vocation Programme, Academic Bank of Credit etc. have been launched to enable the youth of India to become self-reliant and skilled through flexible rules and regulations and the freedom to pursue education at their own pace and viability. In the Union Budget 2025-26, priority has been given to education sector where it has received 2.54 per cent (Rs 1.28 lakh crore) of the total amount, of this Rs 50078 crore has been allocated for higher education. About Rs 68800 crore on skills and Rs 160 crore under PM-Usha scheme, Rs 20000 crore in research development, Prime Minister's Internship Scheme (launched in the Union Budget with a budget of Rs 10831 crore in 2025-26), Grameen Samriddhi Programme, Central Sector Interest Subsidy (CSIS) scheme, etc. have been implemented to raise the standards in higher education and link it to practical life. But the efforts that have been made to build skilled workforce and to ignite the sense of creativity form their study period are really working in that direction? This paper is trying to examine the ground reality of these skills and vocational courses that are being taught at the UG level and what are the barriers at institution level in implementing these courses. For this, a structured questionnaire has been prepared to record the responses of the students selected from the 5 colleges affiliated to CCS University, Meerut and a separate questionnaire have also been prepared to record the answers of the faculty.

Keywords: Students, Teachers, Skill development, Vocational, NEP

Introduction:

Even in ancient times when the methods of teaching were not so advanced, many new techniques were invented in India such as the invention of zero, the origin of Ayurveda, yoga, and the production of cotton etc. Moreover, it is not that the importance of skills and vocational training is being understood only today. They learned various skills such as farming, animal husbandry, carpentry, pottery, weaving, and trade methods during their schooling. Despite their different social beliefs and class, they used to learn archery and war techniques which were helpful in maintaining the harmony and security of the nation. After independence, various initiatives were taken such as the Craftsmen Training Scheme (1950), the National Education Policy (1968), the Work Experience Programme (1968), the Vocational Educational Programme (1976-77), Vocationalisation of Education Scheme (1988),

the National Education Policy (1986) etc. were some of the steps in linking the bookish knowledge with the practical life and the day-to-day needs of the individual or society. All these efforts were being made keeping in mind the fact that education should have relevance with the practical life of a person. Moreover, the sheer size and economic challenges of our country were also the reasons behind preferring such courses and policies that enable the individual to be a skilled person and also reduce the burden of the economy by contributing his labour physically or mentally. However, it is a collective effort, where all countries under an umbrella agency like the United Nations were unanimous to accelerate economic growth at an equal pace. From the launch of the Sustainable Development Goals in 2012 to the year 2025, several initiatives were taken and are still underway to reduce the gap between different segments of the world. Education has always been taken as a weapon which is the first and most essential thing on the way to ignite a sense of self-reliance, alertness, intelligence, and prudence about something. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all under sustainable development goals 4 is the way through which targets are set to disappear disparities in education for different sections of the society.

Objectives of the Study:

- The main objective of this study is to find out the status of the functioning of these courses in any institution.
- To know the inclination of students towards any skill development course.
- To know their perspective on how they grade themselves after completing that particular course.
- To identify the gaps that hinders the successful implementation of these courses at the institutional level.
- To know the usefulness of these courses in employment after completing the course.

Review of Literature:

McGrath and Yamada (2023), observed the prevailing trends regarding development and training through skills and vocational courses. The literature and other

readings about vocational education and training around the world are limited to certain set parameters. As in developing countries it is mainly concerned with improving classrooms, colleges, and curriculum, but it does not directly explain the relationship between these courses and development. Others were related to economic perspectives; some others arose through their own experiences. Its different rules of operation and final are inspired by different ideologies that must be embellished on the way to the successful execution of these courses.

[Diwakar and Ahamad \(2015\)](#), observed the scenario of vocational education and training in the context of India, looking at the enrolment ratio. The paper highlighted the importance of VET in upgrading the living standards of marginalized and disadvantaged sections of society with special reference to women.

[Powell and McGrath \(2019\)](#), discussed that vocational education and training is not just about enabling people for employment and increasing productivity, but that it is more than what is designed. It advocates the importance of healthy living that is associated with growth and VET. It is not just limited to the traditional human capital trend.

[Bosch and Charest \(2009\)](#), Bosch specified the difference between what higher agencies such as UNESCO and the ILO demarcated about VET and what it really means other than the traditional one. They argued that, in higher education, people are also getting trained but the real difference lies in the initial expertise in any field. It also claims that VET has more value in places where it produces high-skilled labour and well-paying jobs rather than in places where labour is low-skilled and low-paying jobs.

[Kazilan, Hamzah and Bakar \(2009\)](#), examined the employability level of students of technical and vocational training institutes. Research has also shown that there is a huge gap between specialized skills and employment. It laid emphasis on developing the methods and skills that the industry or employer needs and also on creating collaboration between industry and institution to prepare skilled workers from students.

[Cavanagh, Shaw and Wang \(2013\)](#), examined the role of general education, technical and vocational education and training and skills development in the

transformation of rural places and communities. Scenarios arising from urbanization, population, industrialization, and migration. And, its impact on the rural population, etc., are the major areas that this paper is concerned with.

Research Methodology:

Research Design: This paper mainly focuses on the current scenario of skill and development courses that are being conducted at the university or college level. The main objective of conducting these courses in higher education is to equip students with a diverse education that is different from what they learn in their traditional courses. Something that enables them to add certain skill traits to their personality so that it can be brought forward to gain economic benefits in the future. But is it really working in the direction it's designed for?

Data Collection: This study is primarily framed on primary data and for this, the questionnaire is designed to collect responses from undergraduate students (Graduation Final Year V semester) and faculty. Students have been selected from five colleges affiliated to CCS University. Stratified random sampling method is used. The total sample size is 250 and the response has been 147. The secondary data has been collected online through various government channels.

Limitations: This study is confined to undergraduate students who are studying traditional courses (B. A, B.SC., B. COM).

A cursory look at the various skilling and vocational initiatives launched before and after NEP 2020 for Tertiary Education:

Skills and vocational training also existed since pre-independence times. The War Technician Training Scheme (Koni Bilaspur, 1940), The Craftsmen Training Scheme (1950), Industrial Training Institutes (1950), The Apprentices Act (1961) etc. were some of the most talked-about initiatives. India's first education policy of 1968 (Kothari Commission) also gave due importance and inclusion to vocational education in general education and secondary level education. In addition, the first formal skill university was the Teamlease Skills University established in Gujarat in 2013. After implementing and adopting the Sustainable Development Goals and Agenda 30 and adopting it as NEP 2020 in India, there are around 13+ Skill Universities operating in the country to upgrade the capabilities

of an individual in the specific field and enhance livelihood opportunities. But according to the global standard, the system behind improving the education system according to the requirements of national and local scenarios is very complex. Regional disparities, whether on geographical basis or on socio-economic basis, are the first and foremost factor in the successful execution of any policy or Programme. And that is why, even after the introduction of the New Education Policy 2020 and its implementation in that comprehensive manner, the aspirations and outcomes are still indistinct. Uttar Pradesh, being the most populous state, is also struggling to keep pace and standards in education as per NEP 2020. Among other states, the GER in Uttar Pradesh is also declining from low to higher education as the most recent data available in 2021-22 for tertiary education is 24.1 per cent of the GER. In India, the standard age to enter college education is considered to be 18 years which goes up to 24 to 25 years in the case of studying traditional courses. If we look at the requirements of different industries, sector and other government services then the eligible individuals ideally get their dream job under this period in most cases, except for those fields in which we need higher specialization or degree such as medicine or teaching. The working age group (15-30 years) population in Uttar Pradesh is about 56 per cent. About 2 to 3 per cent of the working-age population has received formal vocational training. More than that, about 36 percent of the population has received informal training in various skills or occupations through various channels, be it family or other means. Data shows that only 8 to 9 per cent of individuals who graduate from ITIs have succeeded in getting a job as per their aspirations. Therefore, in the large part of the working age population and in it those who are formally skilled through various institutions, there are only a handful and most of the formally trained persons are unable to get the job they desire. It also has a low proportion of girls, where about 60 percent are out of this frame.

Since the introduction of NEP 2020, and before, the two main statutory bodies have been responsible for managing skills and vocational training as separate education and merging it with general education.

Source: <https://www.msde.gov.in/ministry>, <https://nsdcindia.org/>,
<https://www.ugc.gov.in/>

Along with this, Samagra Shiksha is also an initiative launched by the Ministry of Education in 2018, though it covers up to secondary level education. These are some of the initiatives that are going on at full speed for the holistic development of the individual entering formal and informal education. However, the initiatives created by the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship are specifically designed to develop the environment under which the individual finds himself more skilled and can devote himself to a specific occupation or skill. After the adoption of NEP 2020 and to meet the targets set under the Sustainable Development Goals and to match the pace of economic growth like that of advanced countries, India's education has seen a complete transformation from primary level to post-completion of education. The University Grants Commission (UGC) has made progress in this direction and has developed such a mechanism so that general education and traditional courses are also in sync with other high-tech and advanced courses and not just become a monotonous mode of education. But currently it is not working in the same way everywhere across the country because diversity and inequality are more prominent when it comes to education.

Results & Analysis:

This research is trying to understand the purpose, status and outcomes to be found through these (skill development and vocational) courses. However, the global objective of this type of inclusive education is to equip everyone with some kind of skill irrespective of their past performance in education. This is the most unique feature of this NEP 2020 along with some other qualities. It has been 5 years since its inception across the country and it is still struggling in terms of inclusion and equity in education in a comprehensive manner. However, there is a contradiction even in terms of its implementation in an equitable manner.

- For this study, data has been collected from undergraduate students who are in their final year and who have studied these courses during the first and second year. However, the total sample size is 250 and the total response recorded is 147. It's not seemed appropriate to bring out only the student's point of view, but for more realistic research we have also collected information on it from college teachers also (15).
- **Student (Undergraduate Students who are studying traditional courses such as B. A, B.SC & B.COM)-**

B.A	97	66%
B.SC	14	9.5%
B.COM	36	24.5%
Total	147	100%

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 1

Figure - 1

The major students participating in this research study come from these streams. The highest number of these students are from B.A, about 66.7 per cent, followed by B.COM (24.5 per cent) and B.SC (9.5 per cent). The stream-wise classification of students gives us an insight into their inclinations and also shows what they can or cannot do more intuitively and efficiently.

- **Age-wise Classification of Students-**

Class Interval	Frequency	Percent
19-20	101	69
21-22	39	26.5
23-24	7	4.8
Total	147	100

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 2

Figure - 2

They also contribute to 63 to 64 per cent of India’s working age group. There is not much variation as the standard age for starting a college education is 18 years and above. The most prominent age group in this study is 19-20 which is about 70.1 per cent, followed by 21-22 which is 26.5 per cent and the lowest is 23-24 which is 4.8 per cent. This is a time when most students lean towards their careers. So, what they study during this period affects their career choices the most.

- Gender-wise distribution of Students:

Category	Respondent	Percent
MALE	47	32
FEMALE	100	68
Total	147	100

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 3

Figure - 3

Based on the available data, out of 147 students, 68 per cent are female and the remaining 32 per cent are male. Given the national enrolment in the arts stream which stands at 51 per cent, it is important to admit more women in higher studies like men. In addition, it is important because they are less likely than men to enter the workforce or take certain courses after completing their regular studies. In this study they are more prominent and assertive.

- **Region from where they come from:**

Category	Frequency	Percent %
Rural	92	62
Urban	56	38
Total	147	100

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 4

Figure - 4

Most of the students surveyed come from rural areas, including about 62 percent of students and the remaining 38 percent of students come from urban areas. Regional disparities in terms of convenience have always been impressive. Since infrastructure is always better in urban areas due to ease of access and availability of resources, it is natural for them to move to cities to get a good education. In this study, the most influential background is rural.

- District where the college is located:

District	Frequency of Students	Percent
Hapur	67	46
Ghaziabad	52	35
Bulandsahar	28	19
Total	147	100

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 5

Figure - 5

Although most of the students in this study belong to rural areas, this is why they prefer to study in colleges that are adjacent to their place of origin. By looking at this table, it can be ascertained that most of the students' study in colleges that are in Hapur (46 percent), followed by Ghaziabad at 35 percent and Bulandsahar at 19 percent. Compared to the other two cities, Ghaziabad is more developed, which is why they are more vocal about their choice of courses than the other two. It is also clear that developed or large cities are able to provide more facilities than less developed.

- **The Stream in which they have completed their higher secondary education:**

Different Stream	Frequency of Students	Percent %
Arts	72	49
Science	36	24
Commerce	31	21
Other	8	5
Total	147	100

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 6

Figure - 6

Since skills and vocational education are started from their lower secondary level, they are more likely to apply for or opt for courses they are already used to. However, after the introduction of NEP 2020, efforts have been made to bridge any existing gap, be it in the form of streams or regular courses or specific vocation courses. Ultimately, the objective must be achieved. Looking at this table it can be said that most of the students in this study belong to the arts stream (49%), followed by science (24%), commerce (21%) and the rest of the students come from other courses (5%) which is not specified here.

Different skill or vocational courses which they studied in their first two years of graduation:

The skills and vocational courses mentioned below are exclusively offered in colleges. There are a variety of running skills that are primarily designed at the university level, and then it is further introduced to college students. However, it is entirely up to the college administration to implement any skills or vocational courses at the college level and it is completely controlled at the local level after looking at the available infrastructure and other resources.

Yoga
Introduction to Mutual Fund
Introduction to Share Market
Computerised accounting
Patrakarita
Basic communicative English
Principle and practice of banking
Yoga and correctives
Tourism and cultural heritage
Mutural funds and digital marketing
Food and hygiene
DIGITAL MARKETING & ENTREPRENEURSHIP
Certificate course in Computer
Introduction to E-Return & Computerized Accounting & G.S.T.
First aid and health
Indian tribal and folk art
Tourism and travel management
Basic communication English
Social work
Functional Hindi
Journalism and Tourism
Heritage guide

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 7

- Why did you choose these courses for your 1st year and 2nd year of graduation:

Different Reasons	Frequency of Students	Percent %
Due to prior Knowledge	80	54
Based on Interest	54	37
At someone’s Behest	1	1
No other options	12	8
Total	147	100

Source: Field Survey

Table - 8

Figure - 8

It has been observed that students are not much aware of these courses and perhaps they choose courses that are not meant for them. However, looking at this table, it does not seem to be the case as about 54 per cent students have opted for these courses due to prior knowledge, 37 per cent said it is their own interest, for 8 per cent students have no option left and only 1 per cent have chosen this course at someone’s behest.

- **Did you get enough opportunity for hands-on training while pursuing skill and vocational courses:**

Category	Frequency	Percent %
YES	102	69
NO	45	31
Total	147	100

Source: Field Survey

Table - 9

Figure - 9

Looking at this table, it can be assumed that many students (69 Percent) are accepting that they have been provided with ample opportunity to gain practical knowledge on their chosen skills course. The remaining 31 percent of students are experiencing a lack of practical knowledge in their chosen skills course.

- **Were there appropriate resources (instructors, equipment, software, field visit) available for studying the skill or vocational course you choose:**

Category	Frequency	Percent %
YES	91	62
NO	56	38
Total	147	100

Source: Field Survey

Table - 10

Figure - 10

About 62 per cent of the students have been provided with proper infrastructure and instructor during their skilling courses and 38 per cent have not been provided with adequate infrastructure so that they can match the pace with other students to complete this course efficiently.

- **Did you have any prior knowledge about the skill or vocational course you studied:**

Category	Frequency of the Students	Percent %
YES	100	68
NO	47	32
Total	147	100

Source: Field Survey

Table - 11

Figure - 11

It may be matter of discussion that about 68 per cent of the students admitted that they have prior knowledge about the skill course they studied. On the other hand, about 32 per cent of students have no prior knowledge about their skills course.

- **Do you think that you have become proficient enough in this course to be able to get employment on its basis:**

Category	Frequency of the Students	Percent %
YES	107	73
NO	40	27
Total	147	100

Source: Field Survey

Table - 12

Figure - 12

Despite so many contradictions, there are about 73 percent students who see themselves as skilled individuals and want to pursue this skill and get a job. There are about 27 per cent students who think that they are not sufficiently skilled in terms of getting employment on this basis.

- How satisfied are you with the skills or vocational courses you have learned:

Rating	Frequency of Students	Percent %
Satisfied	133	90
Dissatisfied	14	10
Total	147	100

Source: Field Survey

Table - 13

Figure - 13

The emergence and participation of skills and vocational courses in traditional courses seems to be something that those who do not have other access to study these courses can do the same with their regular studies. Therefore, based on the above data, it has been inferred that about 90% of the students are satisfied with the skill and development courses conducted in their institute. On the other hand, about 14 percent students are not satisfied with the courses which are running in their institute.

- **What other problems did you face while pursuing skill and vocational courses? Please specify:**

Problems Faced by the students	Frequency of Students
No Problem	38
Poor quality of Education	2
Limited Access	1
Existing courses are unable to meet current employment needs	2
Gap between skill & demand	3
Money problems & computer problems	5
Lack of practical knowledge & lectures are not well explained	25
Didn't get any classes or training session	12
No experience	2
So many problems (not specified)	1
Lack of critical thinking	1
Irregular classes	10
Lack of teacher guidance	5
Instructor & tools related problem	5
Timing problem	1
Financial condition, societal problems, Maintaining balance between family & studies	1
Distance related problem and transportation	3
Content not available/Lengthy syllabus and short time, Obsolete Syllabus	25
Language barriers and Maintenance	3
Basic is not clear	1
Course choice is not given	1

Source: Field Survey

Table - 14

In our study, the students have talked about the problems they face while studying these courses and looking at this, it can be said that this is not only the matter of their mind but also represents the scenario and opinions of millions of students who are studying in any corner of the state or the country.

Figure - 14

- After pursuing relevant skills or vocational courses, how will you use them in practical life:

Uses of Skill courses post completion of the Undergraduate Degree	Frequency of the student
No Use	35
Teaching	15
To tell others about their benefits	1
The skills will be use when the time comes and they are perfect for a particular situation	1
Not sure	10
For maintaining balance in the life & for understanding the structure of society	3
To live healthy life	4
Applying this knowledge in day-to-day life	2
By doing job	30
Proper management of money	2
In medical & food	1
Need to do some other courses for enhance skill	36
In starting own business	2
For growing confidence	1
For the preparation of competitive exams	1
It enhances my knowledge about Mutual Funds	3
Total	147

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 15

Figure - 15

As far as the use of these courses in the lives of students after completing these courses is concerned, it depends on the type of course one has taken and what is the level.

- **Do you think that after completing college, you will need to pursue other courses to make the skills or vocational courses you have learned employable?**

Category	Frequency of the Students	Percent %
YES	28	44
NO	15	24
Not Sure	20	32
Total	63	100

Source: Field Survey

Table - 16

Students who have gained some types of skill knowledge do not get enough channels to show their potential. Looking at this table, it can be assumed that 44 per cent of the students feel that they need to pursue other courses further to achieve something bigger than this. 32 per cent of the students are in a dilemma whether to continue or not and about 24 per cent of the students do not want to extend this course further to get employment.

Figure - 16

- **As a student, what suggestions would you like to give to improve it:**

What Student want for the improvement in the skill & vocational courses at their institute
Certificate should provide
More opportunities for Hands on training
Qualified & Trained Teachers
Classes should be increase for gaining chances of practical knowledge
Creation of Opportunities for applying knowledge
Increase the availability of Study Material
Exams must be conducted on the given subject matter time to time as to
More skills should be added as per the requirement of the society
Providing proper information and guidelines to the students about the course
Colleges organized weekly programmes for students
Providing opportunity to students to do any activities related to vocational
Teachers should take classes on skills and vocational courses
Availability of student centric curriculum
Better Infrastructure and Equipment

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 17

Teacher's perspective on the skill & vocational courses that are running in their institute:

- What factors did you take into consideration while conducting any skill and vocational courses in your institute?

Different Factors	Frequency of the teachers
College Infrastructure/Resources & Environment	2
Student's Interest/Background	5
Prior knowledge of the student about that course	1
Course must meet the student's requirements	1
Classes should be on time	1
Helps for enhance their physical and mental health	1
Skills that require least investment	2
Courses that might help tap the local resources	4
Lab work and preparation of different chemical	1
Financial Feasibility	5
Practical Utility of the Curriculum	4
Qualified Trainers	6

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 18

Figure - 18

After discussing with some teachers, it has been concluded that we all want to keep in mind many factors such as infrastructure, trained faculty, and student interest etc. and it is the same in all the institutes. Estimates can also be made by looking at this graph.

- **Did you get adequate budget allocation from the authority for starting and smooth implementation of various skill and vocational courses under NEP 2020 in your institute:**

Category	Frequency of the teachers
YES	4
NO	10
Insufficient	2

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 19

Figure - 19

As far as the fund is concerned with regard to skills and smooth functioning of business businesses, it is not provided in the manner it should be. Financial support for these courses is still far-fetched for many institutions.

In your opinion, how effective are the following courses in making students employable:

In most cases, and many institutions do not have the basic resources and infrastructure in the proper way, which is why these courses are not as fruitful as they should be.

- **What do you think are the reasons behind the lack of credibility and quality of these courses at this level:**

Different Factors
Slow implementation of necessary policies at college level
In-adequate staff
Lack of infrastructure/Budget & student's interest
Lack of certification by authorised agencies
Lack of manpower
Lack of collaboration between the institution/Unskilled Teachers
Lack of homework at ground level
Not properly institutionalised
These courses are not added in the final marks, extra burden

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 20

- **What changes can be made to improve the quality of these courses within the available resources and budget:**

For Improving quality and increasing credibility of these courses
Orientation programs
Increase fund/ appointment of skilled staff
Increase interest of students regarding these courses
Certification of the courses by authentic agencies
Flexible learning Environment
Collaboration with the industries
External evaluation of the courses in subjective manner
Proper expertise/ proper management
Project based learning

Source: Primary Survey

Table - 21

Suggestions/Recommendations:

- Since these courses are conducted at the college level, it is important that they are monitored regularly from the respective university.

- To maintain the quality of these courses, it is important to strictly adhere to the motive of the courses, which ignites a sense of self-sufficiency among the individual rather than whitewashing the landscape to hide the real scene.
- It has also been observed that NEP 2020 was implemented in a hurry across the country without creating awareness among the students, which is purely for them. So, the most important thing is to develop the steps that create curiosity and enthusiasm about these courses among the individuals so that they don't take these courses just like a simple course.
- It has also been seen through this study that students are not being given certificates on passing the skill course, although there is a proper system in which their credits are recorded, but giving certificates increases both the quality and credibility of that course.
- The place of origin and background of the students can never be neglected and this becomes even more important when we are directed to reduce all kinds of disparities. In our field of study, most of the students belong to rural backgrounds and there is also variation in terms of financial status. The effort should therefore be focused on employing and adopting curriculum designs that ultimately succeed in producing good work with a good amount of money.
- It has also been observed that students have to pay some fees for their skill courses at the institute level. Therefore, vigilance at the institution level as well as at the university level is imperative to ensure utilization of particular funds in the specified clause.
- We find that most of the institutions have implemented skills and vocational courses that are well suited to their infrastructure and other resources, but in reality, even those specific courses are not executed properly due to the monotonous environment of the surroundings. Therefore, efforts should be made to ensure proper execution of these courses at the institute level so that at least the students have proper theoretical knowledge of their chosen course.
- Skill means having practical knowledge of something that enables a person to live life with self-respect. Because having knowledge, one does not need to wander for anything. So, the importance of practical knowledge and practical training cannot be replaced by good lectures or online study. It

should be provided with the theoretical concept so as to be well versed with something.

- At present, institutions have to manage funds for skills and vocational courses at their own level, so sometimes it spoils the system which also disrupts the functions of various courses. Therefore, the system should work in such a way that it does not discriminate among institutions in terms of providing funds and other facilities.
- The study also found that there is no synergy between the institutions, local industries, regulatory bodies which somehow undermines the purpose of this course. There is a need to create rapprochement between providers and recipients to handle the limitations of funding, infrastructure, and other resources without compromising the purpose of these courses.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be said that the approach behind bringing and merging these courses into general or traditional courses will be more successful when the fundamentals become clearer. In order to improve the employment prospects of the students pursuing these courses, it is necessary to bring changes at the local and institute level and also to explain to the students the real purpose of these courses and what these courses can do for them if they do it in a proper manner. Also, some efforts can be made at the level of the students as they can increase their knowledge level by collecting additional knowledge on it on their behalf.

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